

Micro-Physiological Aspects of Plants Planting *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv.) and *Centrosema Pubescens* (Benth.) For Phytoremediation of Mercury Polluted Land

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Microbiology is a branch of biology that studies microorganisms, especially bacteria, fungi, microscopic algae, protozoa, and archaea. While plant physiology is a branch of biology that studies the cooperation of living systems in the plant body and the response to the influence of the surrounding environment so that the plant can live. These two fields of biology, if studied and explored, can become the latest innovation ideas that are very useful for the survival of living things. One example is the addition of mycorrhizae which have positive benefits on plant growth of *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv.) and *Centrosema Pubescens* (Benth.) for phytoaccumulation of mercury-contaminated land.

Mercury is a heavy metal element that is a very dangerous pollutant. One source of mercury pollution is mining sites. Disposal of mining waste without proper treatment can contaminate the soil around the mining site. This can have a negative impact on the environment around the mine. According to Wiwik and Tri (2015), to minimize the damage, the mining area can be rehabilitated. However, the main obstacles to the rehabilitation of these areas are the low content of organic matter, nutrients, low soil microbial activity (Setiadi, 2003) and the presence of mercury in the groundwater itself (Ekamawanti et al., 2005). Therefore, rehabilitation by utilizing the potential work of the microbial rhizosphere to support plant growth in mercury-contaminated land is an alternative to biotechnology that is environmentally friendly and easy to apply. This technique is called bioremediation of mercury contaminated land. Bioremediation is a process that uses microbes, plants, microbial enzymes or plants to remediate or reduce the toxic nature of pollutants in the soil or environment (Wang, 2004).

According to Muliadi et al (2013), several efforts have been made to overcome environmental pollution by heavy metals such as chemical-physical methods by separating heavy metal ions with ion exchange resins or activated carbon, electrolysis with electrocoagulation and electrokinetics. However, this method is relatively expensive and less effective. Another effort that can be used to reduce or recover heavy metal pollutants is with certain plants that can absorb and accumulate heavy metals with high concentrations, known as phytoremediation. Phytoremediation is a remediation method that relies on the role of plants to absorb, degrade, transform, and mobilize heavy metal pollutants.

According to research by Dwi (2014), plants that can accumulate heavy metals such as mercury are *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv.) and *Centrosema Pubescens* (Benth.) plants. *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv.) can be used as a phytoremediation plant because it can grow quickly on all types of soil. In addition, this plant is drought tolerant with temperatures reaching 36°C. *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv.) plants grow in a convoluted manner and are able to

adapt well to various environmental conditions. According to the Research and Development Ministry of Agriculture (2010), this plant *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv.) can be used as a food source and is able to rehabilitate degraded land, so it has good potential as a phytoremediator plant. Besides *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv), the Sentro plant (*Centrosema pubescens Benth*) is also believed to be a phytoremediation agent. This is because this plant has the ability to adapt to various soil conditions. This plant grows a lot in the gold mining waste disposal environment (Juhaeti, et al 2005). According to Abdari (2013), *Calopogonium Muconoides* has been proven to be a phytoremediation agent for heavy metal mercury by accumulating it in roots, stems and leaves.

However, neither can survive because the accumulated mercury damages plant tissues. One of the efforts to stop this damage is by isolating Mycorrhizae Arbuscula into contaminated soil media. According to Dwi's research (2014), Arbuscula Mycorrhizae inoculated into mercury-contaminated soil media proved to have a good impact on the growth of *Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv.) and *Centrosema Pubescens* (Benth.) plants. According to Dahono et al (2019), Mycorrhizal Arbuscula had a significant effect on plant height, stem diameter and number of leaves. Arbuscula Mycorrhizal fungi are a group of fungi that live in the soil and belong to the endomycorrhizal group that has a hyphal structure called arbuscula. Giving mycorrhizae will meet the initial needs of plant nutrients immediately, which is very necessary in the process of further plant growth. Giving mycorrhizae at a dose of 15 grams gave the best results on plant height, root biomass and soil P content (Harlis et al., 2008). This is possible because of the ability of mycorrhizae to absorb nutrients and water (Abbot et al 1981, Abbot et al 1992).The arbuscula acts as a contact site and transfer of mineral nutrients between the fungus and its host plant in the root cortex tissue. This fungus will attack plant organs that are in the soil so that later the plant will absorb nutrients better. *Planting Calopogonium Muconoides* (Desv), Sentro plants (*Centrosema pubescens Benth*) with the addition of arbuscular mycorrhizal inoculation is expected to provide benefits to the community.

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